

STUDY ON LIAISON OF MORALE, LEADERSHIP AND PRODUCTIVITY

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Abstract:

Morale is a psychological concept. It is intangible in nature but one can observe it from behaviour of a person. We empirically study morale and its effect on the productivity of the organization. We observed that when employees have high morale they give their 100% input towards their job; which in turn shows a very high level of job satisfaction. This continues when the leaders of the organization are motivating in nature. This paper demonstrates how does morale reflects on overall efficiency of the employees, factors affecting morale, effects of morale on productivity, role of leadership in boosting the morale of employees and various other ways of boosting the moral. We wrap up this study with arguments followed by a concluding discussion.

KEYWORDS

Morale, Factors affecting Morale, Effect on Productivity, Role of Leadership, Relationship in Morale, Leadership and Productivity

INTRODUCTION:

According to Dale Yoder, Morale is a feeling somewhat related Spirit, Enthusiasm or Zeal, whereas Edwin defines morale as; a mental condition or attitude of an individual or group which determines their willingness to co-operative.

Morale can be categorized into two types High and Low. Happy employees have high morale while dissatisfied and unhappy employees have low morale. A high morale means the employee is satisfied with the job, puts in efforts, is creative, takes initiative, is committed to organization and focuses on achieving organization goals rather than personal. A low morale is just opposite of that it is the unrest of mind. The objectives of this study is to study the different factors affecting the morale, to learn the effects of morale on the productivity of the organization, to study the role of leadership in boosting the morale of an employee and to examine various ways of boosting the morale. The research mostly uses exploratory research design wherein secondary data sources have been extensively used (Rajesh Timane, 2015). The next sections discuss the factors affecting morale, role of leadership in boosting morale along with effect of morale on employee productivity.

FACTORS AFFECTING MORALE

The most important factor contributing employees morale are: relationship with the fellow workers, team spirit in direct work environment ,working condition of work place ,leaves and holidays provided, management and employees are allowed to talk freely². In the online article by Dallis Perry and Thomas Mohoney on in plant

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² A study on employee morale & its impact on employee efficiency at Jaypee Cement Plant, Rewa By Dr Usha Tiwari in Abhinav International Monthly referred Journal of Research in Management and Tech Vol-3 Issue '2014

communication and employee morale an assumption which apparently underlies much of the importance ascribed to employee communications is that good communications bring about high morale.

When an organization motivates its employees to a high degree, resultant morale in the organization is equally high. Motivation is the process and morale is the product. Therefore, continuous monitoring and improvement of morale is necessary for an organization. In the article on improving the morale by David G Javitch; the author has suggested few ways to improve employee morale. According to him morale is defined as the end result of many factors present in the workplace environment. Some of these factors are the work setting itself, worker satisfaction and action, salary, supervisory input, working conditions, status, and more.

It appears that the morale is also affected by organizational trust. A perusal of recent studies reveals that organizational trust affects the morale and there is a direct relation between organizational trust and employee morale of a particular organization. There are several ways through which managers can increase the organizational trust². Some of the signs of decreased morale are: tardiness, absenteeism, apathy, moping, backstabbing, decreased quality, decreased productivity, increased errors, accidents or injuries a negative event, such as a firing, a promotion of an employee when others are overlooked, or arguments between staff and/or management.

The feeling of a loss of wages, having to pay for medical/dental insurance, and reduced pension is indeed the basis of declining morale at Schnucks grocery stores. A study done on the job satisfaction and morale on Commercial banks in Bangladesh suggests that job satisfaction can affect employee morale, turnover, absenteeism, and pro-social behaviour, which can be crucial for organizational success. This not only applies to traditional business but also the financial institutions like bank. The job satisfaction of employees of the commercial banks is critical for the success.

In the book on personnel management by Dr CB Mamoria the author has listed several criteria in the determination of level of workers morale that includes; the organization itself ; the nature of the work; the level of satisfaction; supervision received; the perception of the self; workers perception of the past awards and future opportunities for rewards; the employees age; the employees educational level and occupational level; this edition also includes assumptions in the understanding of morale, types of morale, effects of morale on productivity and performance and measurement or evaluation of morale and various methods of improving an employee morale. There is a very strong effect of organizational culture and climate on the morale and satisfaction of the employee on the organization. They both reflect the employees' perception of their organization and they are extremely important for the organization to achieve goals.

LEADERSHIP AND MORALE

The study done on the relationship between leadership and employee morale in higher education revealed that there is a relationship between leadership and morale, and those leadership competencies such as communication, fostering trust and team building set a clear direction for the college impact on morale. It is recommended that morale surveys should be conducted to obtain the requisite information before developing strategies that relate to employee morale, retention and performance.

Morale is essential to the success of any organization and leaders are the head to ensuring their organization is headed in the right direction. Influencing by way of leadership power and position may continually be used in any organizational situation and is sometimes needed to achieve the objective. Leaders lead by example and their behaviour alone may express more than words can explain, but one concern is sure and that subordinates do look for positive role models and their leaders doing the right thing. Leaders make decisions all the time, their decisions may not always be right or wrong, but the best decision based on the circumstances given may be better than no decision. Gini in 2004 implied that leaders need to establish their goals with a clear vision and effective communication channel of what they stand for, what they want to achieve, and what they expect from others, and where the organization wants to go.

However leaders are just as an important factor to an organization as are employees and according to Banerji and Krishnan (2000) a leader aligns vision with followers needs and aspirations, propagates open communication and generates team motivation, is a risk taker, helps and coaches in confidence building and promotes team building. Leadership characteristics may start at the home or classroom for some and Stein (2009) states that teachers are

undeniably leaders in the community and in the classroom, they must be able to have some kind of life lasting impact on students and be able to motivate them to strive for excellence.

MORALE AND PRODUCTIVITY

In a study done by Bilva and Nagara, it is clear that various factors which influences morale and productivity of the employees each as Social Security measures, welfare facilities, salary status, Bonus, health condition, shift system and recognition of work are getting much importance. Unless an employee has poor morale if always a possibility of employee disharmony and also affect smooth running of the organization.

By finding this information directly from the persons experiencing the poor morale, the research ensures the problem is being addressed. The survey also shows the employee that the management is very serious about the issues which affect their nature. The issue can lead to poor productivity, increased absences and could become very expensive with operational costs. A study done on employee morale in textile industry; it has been opined by the authors that various interactive behaviors such as interpersonal behaviour, group behaviour, use of power and authority, leadership, communication, conflict and control are the significant factors which affect the climate in an organization thus influencing productivity.

In the book human relations and organization behaviors by Dwivedi; it has been found that morale as a Responsibility of Management (long term effects of morale, gradual changes in morale, ability of people to withstand stress, factors causing fluctuations in morale, expectations of people and reality, morale cannot be permanent) Indices of Low morale (employee unrest, absenteeism and tardiness, employee turnover, grievances, need for discipline, fatigue and monotony) and Indian studies on morale³.

ARGUMENTS

In the article improving staff morale through corporate wellness programme the author opines that one key to staff retention is creating a positive work environment. Making employees feel valued, respected, acknowledged and appreciated fosters loyalty to them and has a positive effect on their morale. One of the many methods of improving your staff morale and teamwork is to incorporate a staff wellness programme into the Companies schedule⁴.

The study done on employee morale in a textile industry identified that the frequent initiatives shall be taken by the management to ensure high morale among the workers in the organization. The initiatives are training, welfare measures, job clarity, cleanliness, safe working conditions, safety measures and rewards & recognition. In one of the article on the website the author concludes a few tactics to think about adapting business to keep employee morale high like; keep employees feeling their work is more than just a job, take time to creatively celebrate accomplishment, grant time off to employees to pursue way of doing things, mix up the companies usual way of doing things, do not forget to have fun, and train employees to develop positive attitudes.

Other ways to reach your de-motivated employees are: Show concern, Provide appropriate feedback, create goals, offer recognition of the employee efforts, provide more challenging tasks, and promote people for achievements. Dr David G suggests another outstanding feature for improving organizational trust among the employees is to pay attention to the promises made to the employees. Managers should pay particular attention towards fulfilling the promises made to the employees as it leads to improved organizational trust and thereby employee morale.

Employee morale plays very important role in every organization. Good employee morale helps to success of the organization. Performance is the key outcome of high morale. Morale can be studied from overall behaviour of an employee. A satisfied worker always has a high level of morale and he helps to increase the productivity. It is necessary to keep the employees happy and keep the smile on their face. Morale is not a permanent phenomenon. It

⁴ *Human relations and organizational behaviour by Dwivedi R S. Macmillan India Ltd, New Delhi*

⁴ *Nawaz, M. (2006, Dec 31st). worklife solution article. (M. M. Nawaz, Ed.) improving staff morale through corporate wellness programme*

keeps on changing. Various factors are responsible for high and low morale but one thing is very sure that happy workers always put their efforts to achieve organizational goals and take the organization to success.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that employees are much satisfied with supervisory relationships as well as they know what their superior expects from them. So they think that they made right choice to work with the organization. It has been found that various factors contribute towards high and low morale. Working condition, workplace environment, relationship and communication between managers and employees, job satisfaction are the other factors which contribute towards high morale; while; tardiness, absenteeism, apathy accident and injuries at workplace decreased the morale.

It is also clear that a high morale of employees improves the performance of organizations. Various other factors that affect morale and productivity are leadership, communication, conflicts, use of power and authority. Moving on, leadership plays very important role in boosting the morale of an employee. Good communication between the leader and employees helps organization achieve its goals and so also the motivation imparted from the leader helps to boost the morale of employees. Various other ways of boosting the employee morale are found to be keeping the work environment positive, making employees feel valued, keep working condition safe, giving proper training and rewards.

We therefore conclude that a motivating leadership helps in enhancing employee morale and hence the performance of the overall organisation. Further, a high morale results in improving employee productivity resulting in performing organisations.

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